

Information on threat types, security dimensions, effectiveness metrics and standardized (yes/no) approaches, corresponding to traditional, technological and innovative training methods.

#	Approach/ Practice	Author(s)	Approach/Practice Description	Type of Approach / Practice	Type of Threat (NIST SP 800-30 Rev. 1)	Security Dimension (MAGERIT 3.0)	Effectiveness Metrics	Standardized (Yes/No)	Studies
1	Cyber Security Awareness Campaigns	Bada, M., Sasse, A.M., Nurse, J.R.C. (2015)	Design campaigns aligned with risks to change behavior by providing simple, consistent rules that are easy to follow. The objective is to influence human behavior to reduce risky actions, enhancing overall cybersecurity awareness in healthcare settings.	Campaigns / Cyber campaigns	Adversarial (Individual: Outsider, Insider; Group: Ad hoc) - e.g., phishing or social engineering exploiting user behavior.	Confidentiality, Authenticity, Traceability - e.g., protecting patient data, verifying information sources, and tracking user actions.	Not detailed in the study	No - General campaigns not tied to a specific standard; tailored to organizational needs.	Luiza Fabisiak et al. (2020)
2	Cybersecurity awareness campaigns	Gordon et al (2019)	Campaigns aimed at raising awareness among healthcare staff about cyber risks. The objective is to educate staff on recognizing threats like phishing and ransomware, using methods like simulated attacks and informational materials.	Campaigns / Cyber campaigns	Adversarial (Individual: Outsider, Insider; Group: Ad hoc) – e.g., ransomware campaigns exploiting lack of awareness.	Confidentiality (protecting sensitive information), Availability (preventing disruptions from ransomware).	Measured by 1. Participation rates and 2. Effectiveness in identifying threats during simulations.	No – Described as organization- specific without reference to standards.	Ying He et al. (2021)

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3	Classroom-Based Training	Ali (2019), Carella et al. (2017), Kim et al. (2016), Khader (2021), Churi and Rao (2021), Luburic et al. (2019), Cai and Amey (2017), Konstantinou (2020), Tran et al. (2023)	Delivers cybersecurity education through face-to-face or virtual instruction. Aims to enhance understanding of cyber threats and reduce susceptibility (e.g., to phishing). Incorporates flipped classroom and gamified approaches for flexibility and engagement.	Classroom workshops / In person / Instruction-led training	Adversarial (Individual: Insider, Trusted Insider) - e.g., employees falling for social engineering.	Confidentiality (protecting data discussed in training), Integrity (accurate threat knowledge), Authenticity (verifying user actions)	1. Improved student understanding (G. A. Ali, 2019), 2. Reduced phishing susceptibility (A. Carella et al., 2016), 3. Comparative benefits of gamified learning (T. Wu et al., 2021), 4. Hands-on experience value (P. Kim et al, 2016).	No - No evidence of formal standardization; varies by institution.	Saif Al-Dean Qawasmeh et al. (2024)
4	Instructor-Led (Brown-Bag Seminars, Classroom Workshops)	Not specified (Evaluated by Ghazvini & Shukur within TMS Framework)	Involves face-to-face training sessions, led by instructors to educate employees on information security. Aimed at fostering direct interaction and discussion. The TMS Map suggests moderate engagement but higher supervision needs.	Classroom workshops / In person / Instruction-led training	Accidental (User): Errors from lack of knowledge, such as improper email handling. Example: An employee falling for a phishing email due to not understanding risks taught in a seminar.	Confidentiality: Teaches protection of sensitive data. Integrity: Promotes correct data handling practices. Authenticity: Covers authentication practices.	Prior HUKM programs using traditional methods failed to produce desired outcomes, indicating limited effectiveness (no specific metrics).	Yes: A standard training method used across industries, though not uniquely standardized in the study	Arash Ghazvini et al. (2017)

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5	E-learning	Abawajy (2012)	Provides digital learning modules to educate employees on cybersecurity risks and best practices. The objective is to offer self-paced, interactive content that enhances understanding of security policies and fosters secure behaviors, tailored to different knowledge levels.	E-learning	Accidental (User, Privileged User/Administrator): Errors like improper data sharing or misconfiguration by staff (e.g., leaving sessions open in shared environments).	Confidentiality, Integrity, Availability: Safeguards patient data, ensures system reliability, and maintains data accuracy (e.g., proper EHR handling).	1. Module completion rates, 2. Performance in interactive assessments, 3. Reduction in policy violations. 4. Metrics include tracking user progress and error rates in simulated scenarios.	No: Varies widely in design and content, not governed by a universal standard.	Arash Ghazvini et al. (2016)
6	Mandatory Refreshing E-learning Courses	Luiza Fabisiak et al. (2020).	Establish periodic (e.g., annual) mandatory e-learning courses to refresh and update cybersecurity knowledge. The purpose is to ensure continuous learning, reinforce best practices, and keep professionals updated on evolving threats, minimizing human errors.	E-learning	Accidental (User) - e.g., users inadvertently clicking malicious links due to lack of awareness.	Confidentiality, Integrity, Availability - e.g., preventing accidental data breaches, ensuring accurate records, and maintaining system access.	Not explicitly detailed	No - Not described as standardized; a general recommendation for periodic training.	Luiza Fabisiak et al. (2020)

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7	DeCarlo Gamified Training	DeCarlo, Sean M.	A gamified cybersecurity training strategy applied to healthcare workers to improve cybersecurity awareness, focusing on recognizing and mitigating cyber threats through interactive and engaging methods tailored to healthcare professionals. The purpose is to enhance knowledge retention, motivation, and proactive incident reporting compared to traditional training.	Game-based learning	Adversarial (Individual: Outsider, Insider), Accidental (User) - Addresses threats like phishing, ransomware, and user errors common in healthcare settings (e.g., clicking malicious links or mishandling sensitive data).	Confidentiality (protecting patient data), Integrity (ensuring data accuracy), Availability (maintaining access to critical systems).	1. Pre/Post-Test Assessment Scores: This metric evaluates immediate knowledge acquisition and retention, a common measure of training effectiveness. The 13-question assessment covered key cybersecurity concepts such as identifying sensitive data, HIPAA compliance, de-identification, and secure email practices. 2. Number of Security Incidents: This metric measures the practical application of training by tracking real-world security incidents, directly linking training to behavioral outcomes and threat reduction. Incidents were defined as DLP-flagged events, such as sending sensitive data externally 3. Percentage of Security Incidents: By normalizing incidents against total traffic, this metric accounts for differences in data-handling activity, providing a fair comparison of training effectiveness across groups with varying workloads.	No - No evidence in the document of alignment with formal cybersecurity standards (e.g., ISO/IEC 27032 or NIST). It appears as a research-based initiative.	Ana Carreiro et al. (2024)
8	Computer Games	Cone et al. (2007), Monk et al. (2010), Nagarajan et al. (2012)	Utilizes interactive gaming to engage employees in cybersecurity training, aiming to educate about risks and promote secure behaviors through immersive, scenario-based activities. The objective is to make learning engaging and memorable, encouraging application of security concepts in daily tasks.	Game-based learning	Accidental (User): Employees may unintentionally cause breaches due to lack of awareness (e.g., clicking phishing links).	Confidentiality, Integrity, Authenticity: Protects sensitive data, ensures data accuracy, and verifies user actions (e.g., recognizing legitimate vs. malicious emails).	1. User engagement levels, 2. knowledge retention rates, 3. Frequency of security incidents post-training. 4. Metrics include pre/post-training quizzes and monitoring user behavior changes (e.g., reduced phishing click rates).	No: Not standardized; implementation varies by organization and lacks a universal framework.	Arash Ghazvini et al. (2016)

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9	Crossword Puzzles	Not explicitly attributed to a specific author in the document	Employs gamified puzzles to reinforce cybersecurity concepts, making learning engaging and interactive. The objective is to improve retention of security policies and encourage employees to think critically about security risks in a fun format.	Game-based learning	Accidental (User): Errors due to lack of awareness (e.g., failing to recognize social engineering tactics).	Integrity, Authenticity: Ensures correct application of security knowledge and validates user understanding (e.g., identifying phishing attempts).	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Puzzle completion rates, 2. Accuracy in solving security-related questions 3. User engagement feedback. 4. Metrics include time spent and error rates in puzzles. 	No: Highly customized and not part of a standardized training framework.	Arash Ghazvini et al. (2016)

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10	CyberMed Guardians (CG)	Collins Poku Obeng et al. (2024)	A card game designed to enhance cybersecurity awareness among biomedical engineering students by simulating cyber-attacks and defenses in a virtual healthcare network. Players act as cybersecurity analysts, divided into Attackers and Defenders, to learn about common cyber threats, attack vectors, and defense strategies pertinent to healthcare IT systems and medical IoT devices. The game aims to foster engagement, critical thinking, and knowledge retention through interactive gameplay.	Game-based learning	Adversarial (Individual: Outsider, Insider; Group: Ad hoc, Established; Organization: Competitor, Nation-State) – Examples: Malware, phishing, man-in-the-middle, DDoS, insider threats, ransomware targeting healthcare networks.	Confidentiality (protecting patient data), Integrity (ensuring medical device data accuracy), Availability (maintaining healthcare system uptime), Authenticity (verifying user/device identity), Traceability (tracking attack origins)	1. Student Engagement: Measured through observed participation, enthusiasm, and critical thinking during gameplay. 2. Knowledge Retention: Assessed via student feedback surveys indicating improved retention due to interactive, scenario-based learning. 3. Comparison with Traditional Methods: Evaluated through student preferences for the game over lectures, highlighting its engaging and effective nature.	No – The game is a custom-developed educational tool for a specific course, not a standardized framework or product.	Collins Poku Obeng et al. (2024)

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11	Threats and Trade-offs (T&T)	Kseniya Stsiampkouskaya et al. (2025)	A tabletop board game simulating a digital healthcare start-up, where players make decisions on cybersecurity, product innovation, and customer acquisition under resource constraints. It aims to educate players on cyber-attacks, their consequences, and countermeasures while integrating business management concepts. The game fosters awareness of cybersecurity trade-offs and decision-making in a realistic organizational context.	Game-based learning	Adversarial: Individual (Outsider, Insider), Group (Ad hoc, Established), Organization (Competitor, Supplier). Examples: Social engineering, ransomware, DDoS, supply chain attacks, industrial sabotage, targeting employees and doctors. Accidental: User (e.g., employees or doctors mishandling data due to lack of training).	Confidentiality: Protecting patient data in the cloud database. Integrity: Ensuring accurate data transmission from smart pills to the cloud. Availability: Preventing service disruptions from DDoS attacks. Authenticity: Verifying user access via multifactor authentication. Traceability: Tracking data flow through the healthcare system.	Qualitative Metrics.- 1. Content analysis of audio-recorded player interactions 2. Post-game debriefs identified five themes (learning about cybersecurity, business development, motivations for cybersecurity investment, player enjoyment, semblance of reality). Quantitative Metrics.- 1. Post-game survey with self-reported cybersecurity knowledge (mean 5.438, scale 0-10), 2. Game enjoyment (mean 8.813), and game concept (mean 8). 3. Observed decision-making strategies (proactive vs. reactive) and investment patterns (e.g., timing of secure-by-design reader purchase).	No: The game is a custom-developed research and educational tool, not aligned with specific cybersecurity standards (e.g., ISO/IEC 27001). It is licensed under CC BY-NC, indicating non-commercial use and no formal standardization.	Kseniya Stsiampkouskaya et al. (2025)
12	NetWars	SANS (2015)	A Game-based learning involving skill assessment, defensive strategies (system assessment, penetration prevention), and offensive strategies (system penetration scenarios). Designed to simulate real-world cyber-attacks for skill development.	Game-based learning	Adversarial (Individual: Privileged Insider, Nation-State) - Example: Penetration scenarios mimic insider or state-sponsored attacks.	Confidentiality (protecting sensitive data), Availability (maintaining system access)	NetWars and other commercial approaches use a variety of metrics, methods, and tools to evaluate cybersecurity training effectiveness, including: 1. Phishing simulation results, 2. Quiz scores, 3. Pre-training/post-training assessments. 4. Security incident metrics, 5. Employee feedback, 6. Compliance metrics, 7. Participation rates to gain a holistic understanding of program effectiveness	Yes - SANS is known for standardized cybersecurity training aligned with frameworks like NIST; NetWars likely follows similar rigor.	Mackenzie Adams et al. (2015)

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13	Micro Games	Wombat (2015)	A Game-based learning providing basic knowledge, general assessment, and defensive strategies (penetration detection, password management). Aims to enhance employee awareness and basic cybersecurity skills.	Game-based learning	Accidental (User), Adversarial (Individual: Outsider) - Example: Focuses on detecting phishing or managing passwords to counter user errors and external attacks.	Confidentiality (preventing data exposure), Integrity (ensuring password integrity)	To evaluate the effectiveness of cybersecurity training and awareness programs, organizations use a variety of metrics, methods, and tools. These include: 1. Pre- and post-training assessments, 2. Phishing simulation results, 3. Quiz scores, 4. Security incident metrics, 5. Employee feedback, 6. Compliance metrics 7. Completion rates.	Yes - Wombat's platform is a commercial product with structured training, likely aligned with industry standards.	Mackenzie Adams et al. (2015)
14	Gamification	Holdsworth & Apeh (2017); Alotaibi, Furnell, Stengel, & Papadaki (2017); Labuschagne, Veerasamy, Burke, & Eloff (2011); Tioh & Mina (2015)	Uses game design principles to make cybersecurity training engaging, simulating threats to improve retention.	Game-based learning	Adversarial (Individual: Outsider, Insider) - e.g., identity theft, password management issues.	Confidentiality, Integrity, Authenticity - Enhances protection and verification skills.	1. User engagement; 2. Knowledge retention rates; 3. Behavioral change in simulations.	No - Recognized but not standardized in NIST 800-50.	Prince Zaquie et al. (2023)

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15	Serious Game for Healthcare	Ghazvini and Shukur (2018)	A serious game designed for healthcare industry employees to increase information security awareness through interactive scenarios.	Game-based learning	Accidental (User): Addresses errors like mishandling patient data. Adversarial (Individual - Outsider): Includes phishing or social engineering scenarios.	Confidentiality, Integrity, Authenticity: Protects patient data, ensures data accuracy, and verifies user actions.	<p>a) Game Scores and Achievement Tracking: The primary quantitative metric is the game score, which reflects the percentage of correct answers provided by players for each of the eight topics (phishing, web using, email and spam, malicious code, password protection, privacy and confidentiality, workstation and hacking, access control).</p> <p>b) Number of Plays per Topic: The total number of times a topic is played by each employee until achieving a 100% score is recorded. This metric indicates the difficulty level of topics and the learning effort required.</p> <p>c) Lowest and Highest First-Attempt Scores: The lowest and highest scores achieved by employees on their first attempt for each topic are tracked to gauge initial knowledge levels and variability.</p> <p>d) Performance Improvement in Post-Training: A second-round pilot test conducted three months after the initial training compares employee performance to assess knowledge retention and long-term impact.</p> <p>e) Qualitative Feedback from Participants: Feedback was collected from various groups, including three computer science professors, five computer science students, and five HUKM employees, focusing on gameplay experience, attraction, graphics, and overall impressions.</p> <p>f) Employee Progress Monitoring: The game allows instructors and IT managers to view detailed employee progress in the player's profile, including scores, number of plays, and challenging topics.</p> <p>g) Certificate of Accomplishment: A certificate is awarded when employees achieve 100% scores for all eight topics, serving as a motivational and evaluative metric.</p> <p>h) Dynamic Content and Engagement: The game's</p>	No: Game is tailored for a specific healthcare context, not standardized.	Mostafa Sadeghi et al. (2024)

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16	Riskio	Stephen Hart et al. (2020)	A tabletop card game designed to increase cybersecurity awareness by allowing players to assume roles of attackers and defenders in a fictitious organization (University Fees Office). Players use attack, defense, and information cards to learn about cyber threats and countermeasures, guided by a game master who facilitates discussion and provides feedback. The game aims to convey the breadth of vulnerabilities, improve understanding of countermeasures, and allow practice of attack and defense strategies, adaptable to various training needs.	Game-based learning	Adversarial: Individual (Outsider, Insider) – e.g., spear-phishing attacks targeting office manager John (Example 4.1). Accidental: User – e.g., staff plugging in an infected USB drive (Example 4.3).	Confidentiality.- Information disclosure threats (e.g., phishing to steal credentials). Integrity.- Tampering threats (e.g., altering data via application vulnerabilities). Availability.- Denial of Service threats (e.g., botnet attacks). Authenticity.- Spoofing threats (e.g., impersonating IT support). Traceability.- Non-Repudiation threats (e.g., attacks on logging functionality).	Evaluated through Technology Acceptance Model (TAM): 1. Perceived Ease of Use 2. Perceived Usefulness 3. Intention to Use 4. Post-task questionnaires 5. Informal feedback sessions to identify likes/dislikes.	No – The game is a custom-designed educational tool, not based on a formal standard like ISO 27001 or NIST, though it incorporates elements from standardized frameworks (e.g., STRIDE, Cyber Essentials).	Stephen Hart et al. (2020)

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17	Cyber Security- Requirement s Awareness Game	Yasin, A et al 2019	A tabletop card game educating on cybersecurity risks in hospital scenarios. Players identify and exploit vulnerabilities for insider/outsider attacks, with discussions to evaluate attack scenarios.	Game-based learning	Adversarial: Individual (Insider, Outsider) – e.g., insider attacks in hospital systems.	Confidentiality: Patient data breaches. Integrity: Tampering with medical records. Availability: Disrupting hospital services.	1. Quantitative Metrics: a) The 90% feasibility rate of hypothetical scenarios and b) Pre-post questionnaire improvements provide measurable evidence of learning outcomes. 2. Qualitative Metrics: a). Feedback sheets, b). Observations, and c). Discussion sessions offer insights into engagement, d). Collaboration, and e). Practical application of security knowledge.	No – A custom game, not based on a standard threat taxonomy like STRIDE.	Stephen Hart et al. (2020)

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18	InfoSecure Serious Game	Arash Ghazvini et al. (2017)	A serious game developed to deliver information security awareness training at HUKM. It combines educational content with a fun, interactive interface to engage employees. The game consists of 8 subgames covering topics like phishing, password protection, and privacy. Players answer multiple-choice questions, aiming to eliminate “viruses” by selecting correct answers. The game is dynamic, allowing instructors to customize content and graphics, and requires 100% correct answers to complete subgames, with random question ordering to enhance learning. The conceptual model is based on Yusoff (2010).	Game-based learning	Accidental (User): Mistakes by employees, such as using weak passwords or mishandling sensitive data, due to insufficient training. Example: An employee sharing a password with a colleague, unaware of security policies.	Confidentiality: Prevents unauthorized access to EHR (e.g., via strong password practices). Integrity: Reduces errors that could corrupt EHR data. Authenticity: Reinforces user authentication policies. Traceability: Tracks user progress through scores and performance record	1. Player scores (e.g., 0% to 100%), 2. Number of replays (e.g., phishing subgame replayed up to 4 times) 3. Completion rates (100% score required).	No: Custom-developed for HUKM, not a widely standardized product, though based on Yusoff’s (2010) model. It lacks universal standardization across organizations.	Arash Ghazvini et al. (2017)

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19	Game-Based	Not specified (Evaluated by Ghazvini & Shukur within TMS Framework; InfoSecure is a specific instance)	Uses interactive games to deliver security training, combining education with entertainment. Aimed at high engagement and learning through simulation. The TMS Map highlights fun, motivation, and challenge. InfoSecure is the implemented example at HUKM.	Game-based learning	Accidental (User): Errors from lack of awareness, such as mishandling passwords. Example: An employee sharing a password, unaware of policies, mitigated by game-based learning.	Confidentiality: Prevents unauthorized access. Integrity: Reduces data errors. Authenticity: Teaches authentication. Traceability: Tracks progress in games	Not detailed in the study	Yes: Recognized as a standard method in security training literature, though specific games vary.	Arash Ghazvini et al. (2017)
20	Hands-on Laboratories	Luiza Fabisiak et al. (2020)	Incorporate practical, interactive sessions in cybersecurity training to simulate real-world scenarios, allowing medical professionals to practice identifying and responding to cyber threats in a controlled environment. The objective is to enhance practical skills and reinforce theoretical knowledge.	Hands-on training	Adversarial (Individual: Outsider, Insider; Group: Ad hoc, Established) - e.g., phishing simulations to counter social engineering attacks.	Confidentiality: preventing unauthorized access to patient data Integrity: ensuring data accuracy, Authenticity: verifying email authenticity.	Not explicitly detailed in the study	No - Not referenced as a standardized method; proposed as a general training enhancement without specific standards.	Luiza Fabisiak et al. (2020)

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21	Real-time Demonstrations of Past Cyberattacks	Luiza Fabisiak et al. (2020)	Conduct demonstrations by cybersecurity professionals to showcase real examples of past cyberattacks (e.g., ransomware attacks). The purpose is to illustrate attack mechanisms and consequences, increasing awareness of threat severity and motivating adherence to security practices.	Hands-on training	Adversarial (Organization: Competitor, Nation-State) - e.g., ransomware attacks encrypting hospital databases.	Availability, Confidentiality - e.g., ensuring data access and preventing data leaks during ransomware incidents.	Not explicitly detailed	No - Not linked to any specific standard; a bespoke training suggestion.	Luiza Fabisiak et al. (2020)
22	Web-based Sessions	Abawajy (2012), Cone et al. (2007)	Delivers cybersecurity training through online platforms, offering flexibility with instructor-led or self-paced formats. The purpose is to provide accessible, scalable training to educate employees on security policies and practices, enhancing awareness and compliance.	Online Discussion / Training	Accidental (User): Users may misconfigure systems or mishandle data due to inadequate training (e.g., weak password creation).	Confidentiality, Availability, Traceability: Ensures data protection, system accessibility, and audit trails for user actions (e.g., tracking policy adherence).	1. Completion rates, 2. Quiz scores, 3. Application of learned skills in daily tasks. 4. Metrics include user feedback surveys and system logs showing compliance with security protocols.	No: Lacks standardization due to diverse formats and content tailored to organizational needs.	Arash Ghazvini et al. (2016)

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23	Online (E-mail, Web-Based Training, Online Discussion)	Not specified (Evaluated by Ghazvini & Shukur within TMS Framework)	Uses digital platforms like email campaigns, web-based modules, or online forums to deliver security training. Aimed at accessibility and scalability. The TMS Map indicates good content updatability but variable engagement.	Online Discussion / Training	Accidental (User): Mistakes due to insufficient training, such as weak password use. Example: An employee using a predictable password due to not completing an online module.	Confidentiality: Protects EHR data through training. Integrity: Reduces data errors via education. Authenticity: Reinforces secure authentication	Not specified in the document.	Yes: Common in organizational training, following standard e-learning practices, but not uniquely standardized here.	Arash Ghazvini et al. (2017)
24	Paper-Based (Posters and Newsletters)	Not specified (Evaluated by Ghazvini & Shukur within TMS Framework)	Involves distributing posters and newsletters to raise information security awareness. Aimed at providing static, visual reminders of security policies and best practices to employees. The TMS Map indicates limited engagement and interactivity, suitable for broad coverage but less effective for in-depth learning.	Posters / e-posters	Accidental (User): Employees' unintentional errors due to lack of awareness, such as ignoring security policies. Example: An employee mishandling sensitive data due to not reading a policy poster	Confidentiality: Reminds employees to protect sensitive data. Integrity: Encourages proper data handling to prevent errors.	Not specified in the document.	Yes: Common, widely used method in various organizations, following standard awareness practices, but not specifically standardized in the study.	Arash Ghazvini et al. (2017)

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25	Teleconferencing	Not explicitly attributed to a specific author in the document	Uses virtual meetings to deliver cybersecurity training, enabling real-time interaction and discussion. The purpose is to facilitate collaborative learning, clarify security policies, and address specific organizational risks, ensuring employees understand their roles in security.	Presentations / conferences / Teleconferencing	Accidental (User): Employees may overlook security protocols during remote work (e.g., unsecured network usage).	Confidentiality, Authenticity: Protects sensitive communications and verifies participant identities (e.g., secure teleconference setups).	1. Participation rates, 2. Comprehension test scores, 3. Feedback on session relevance. 4. Metrics include attendance logs and post-session policy adherence rates.	No: Implementation depends on organizational tools and lacks a standardized protocol.	Arash Ghazvini et al. (2016)
26	Role-playing Activities	Luiza Fabisiak et al. (2020)	Implement role-playing exercises to demonstrate persuasion techniques used by cybercriminals, such as social engineering tactics. The objective is to train medical professionals to recognize and resist manipulative tactics, reducing susceptibility to attacks like phishing.	Role-playing Training	Adversarial (Individual: Outsider, Insider) - e.g., social engineering attacks tricking users into revealing credentials.	Authenticity, Confidentiality - e.g., verifying the legitimacy of email requests and protecting sensitive data.	Not explicitly detailed	No - Proposed as a creative training method without reference to standards.	Luiza Fabisiak et al. (2020)

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27	Cyber Defence Exercises (CDXs)	Granåsen et al. (2019)	Interactive training programs using real-life scenarios in a controlled environment to enhance cybersecurity skills, particularly for cybersecurity personnel, but also applicable to legal and forensic work. Aims to improve practical response to cyber threats through simulated exercises.	Simulation-based methods	Adversarial (Insider, Outsider): Simulated attacks mimic insider or external hacker actions (e.g., phishing, malware). Accidental (User): Addresses errors like clicking malicious links due to lack of awareness.	Confidentiality, Integrity, Availability: Protects sensitive data, ensures system reliability, and maintains service uptime during attacks.	Team effectiveness measured through: 1. Technical performance 2. Behavioral assessments in simulated scenarios.	Yes: CDXs are structured, repeatable programs often used in military and organizational settings, indicating standardization.	Shahriar Akter et al. (2022)
28	Simulation of Attacks	Not specified (general reference, Caldwell, 2016)	Uses real-world attack simulations to train employees on responding to cyber threats, aiming to build a security mindset and improve practical response capabilities. Includes scenarios like phishing or malware attacks.	Simulation-based methods	Adversarial (Outsider, Group): Simulates external attacks like phishing or ransomware. Accidental (User): Addresses errors in handling suspicious content.	Confidentiality, Integrity, Availability: Protects data from leaks, ensures system integrity, and maintains operational continuity.	No specific effectiveness evaluation frameworks provided.	No: Presented as a general practice without mention of standardized procedures or certifications.	Shahriar Akter et al. (2022)
29	Simulation-Based	Not specified (Evaluated by Ghazvini & Shukur within TMS Framework)	Uses simulated environments to train employees on security scenarios, allowing safe practice of responses. The TMS Map notes high engagement and learning from mistakes.	Simulation-based methods	Accidental (User): Errors due to lack of practice, such as mishandling phishing attempts. Example: An employee clicking a phishing link, mitigated by simulated practice.	Confidentiality: Protects data through practice. Integrity: Reduces errors via training. Authenticity: Reinforces authentication skills.	Not specified in the document.	Yes: A recognized method in security training, though not uniquely standardized here.	Arash Ghazvini et al. (2017)

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30	Security Awareness Training for End Users	SANS Institute	A course designed to ensure compliance and change user behavior, teaching end users to “know” and “do” the right thing consistently. Aims to reduce human error in cybersecurity through targeted education.	Training Platform	Adversarial (Individual: Outsider, Insider; Group: Ad hoc, Established; Organization: Competitor, Nation-State) – Examples: Malware, phishing, man-in-the-middle, DDoS, insider threats, ransomware targeting healthcare networks.	Confidentiality (protecting patient data), Integrity (ensuring medical device data accuracy), Availability (maintaining healthcare system uptime), Authenticity (verifying user/device identity), Traceability (tracking attack origins)	Designed to change user behavior, but no specific metrics provided in the document.	No – The game is a custom-developed educational tool for a specific course, not a standardized framework or product.	David T. Croasdell et al. (2018)

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31	THREAT- ARREST	Hatzivasilis et al. (2021)	Uses modern training methods (emulation, simulation, serious gaming, synthetic data fabrication) to enhance learning for cybersecurity training.	Training Platform	Adversarial (Outsider, Insider): Simulates various cyber-attacks.	Confidentiality, Integrity, Availability: Protects data and system functionality.	The key metrics and approaches used are: a) Individual Trainee Performance Assessment: 1. Performance in Specific Courses 2. Cognitive Profile Evaluation 3. Post-Training Awareness Evaluation b) Program-Wide Efficacy Metrics: 1. Continuous Program Evaluation 2. Runtime Program Adaptation 3. Security Posture Improvement c) Serious Games and Behavioral Metrics: 1. Engagement and Compliance with Security Policies 2. Knowledge Retention 3. Motivation and Learning Transfer. d) System and Scenario-Based Metrics: 1. Scenario Progress and Component Interaction 2. Assurance Model Validation 3. Realism and Relevance of Training e) Organizational Impact Metrics: 1. Reduction in Non-Compliance 2. Workplace Application of Skills 3. Cross-Domain Validation	Yes: EU-funded, standardized framework.	Fulvio Frati et al. 2023

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32	CYRA	Smyrlis et al. (2021)	A model-driven cyber range assurance platform for adaptive cybersecurity training.	Training Platform	Adversarial (Outsider, Insider): Adapts to evolving threats.	Confidentiality, Integrity, Availability: Ensures robust system protection.	<p>The CYRA platform evaluates cybersecurity training effectiveness through a multifaceted approach:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Individual Metrics: Focus on trainee performance in scenarios, quiz scores, incident response accuracy, and behavioral compliance in serious games. 2. Program Metrics: Assess overall program efficacy via aggregated performance data, runtime adaptation based on completion times and scores, and security posture improvements. 3. System Metrics: Track scenario progress, assumption violations, and success in realistic attack simulations. 4. Organizational Metrics: Measure compliance with security policies, learning transfer to the workplace, and achievement of KPIs like vulnerability reduction. 5. Qualitative Metrics: Include user feedback on usability and satisfaction, reinforcing the platform's practical effectiveness. 	No: Research-based, not explicitly standardized.	Fulvio Frati et al. 2023

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33	AERAS Platform	Frati et al.	A virtual cyberwarfare solution for the healthcare sector, simulating security controls and offering hands-on training on their development, assessment, use, and management.	Training Platform	Adversarial (Outsider, Insider), Accidental (User): Addresses phishing, malware, human errors.	Confidentiality, Integrity, Availability, Authenticity: Protects patient data and system access.	The AERAS platform's design and user requirements suggest a comprehensive evaluation approach: 1. Individual Metrics: Focus on trainee performance (e.g., completion rates, accuracy in simulations, quiz scores) and behavioral changes (e.g., reduced use of insecure communication, compliance with breach notifications). 2. Organizational Metrics: Measure threat reduction (e.g., fewer incidents, reduced downtime), improved security posture (e.g., fewer vulnerabilities), and monitoring system effectiveness (e.g., faster threat resolution). 3. Program Metrics: Assess training engagement (e.g., attendance, satisfaction), adaptability (e.g., frequency of adjustments), and evaluation method efficacy (e.g., simulation vs. written test performance). 4. Long-Term Metrics: Track sustained improvements in awareness, compliance, and incident rates over time.	No: Under development, not yet standardized.	Fulvio Frati et al. 2023
34	SETA Programs	Whitman, M. E., Mattord, H. J. (2014)	Security Education, Training, and Awareness (SETA) programs aim to enhance organizational security by increasing employees' knowledge and developing skills to perform their jobs more securely. These programs combine education, training, and awareness activities to motivate employees and foster a security-conscious culture.	Training Program	Adversarial (Individual: Insider, Trusted Insider) – e.g., employees unintentionally clicking phishing links due to lack of awareness.	Confidentiality (the safeguarding of sensitive organizational information), Integrity (the assurance of data precision), Availability (the preservation of system accessibility).	No specific metrics mentioned in the document; effectiveness implied through increased knowledge and skills, but not quantified.	Yes – SETA is a standardized framework widely recognized in information security literature and NIST guidelines (e.g., NIST SP 800-50).	Johan Lugnet et al. (2020)

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35	Cybersecurity training programs	Gordon et al (2019)	Structured programs designed to educate healthcare staff on identifying and responding to cyber threats, such as phishing. The objective is to increase awareness and reduce the likelihood of successful attacks by training staff to recognize malicious activities. Includes sending fake phishing emails to test staff vigilance.	Training Program	Adversarial (Individual: Outsider, Insider) – e.g., phishing emails targeting staff to steal credentials.	Confidentiality (the safeguarding of patient information from unauthorized access), Integrity (the assurance that data remains unaltered)	Evaluation through success rates in identifying fake phishing emails during training campaigns. 1. Overall Click Rates: 2. Per-Campaign Click Rates 3. Comparison of Click Rates Between Offenders and Nonoffenders 4. Trend Analysis of Click Rates Over Time	No – Not explicitly standardized, though aligned with general cybersecurity training practices.	Ying He et al. (2021)

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36	Comprehensive employee training and education	Alzahrani,20	Training and education programs focused on enabling healthcare staff to identify and assess cyber risks, particularly COVID-19-themed social engineering attacks. The objective is to empower employees to mitigate risks through informed decision-making.	Training Program	Adversarial (Individual: Outsider, Insider) – e.g., social engineering attacks using COVID-19 themes.	Confidentiality (protecting patient data from phishing), Integrity (preventing data manipulation).	<p>1. Game-Based Delivery Methods:</p> <p>a) Improvement in Understanding Specific Security Concepts</p> <p>b) Heuristics Evaluation Ratings: Game-based learning achieved higher ratings in the heuristics evaluation process, specifically in: Awareness Levels, Usability, c) Learning Content, Fun and Enjoyability Features</p> <p>d) Preference for Gamified Environments.</p> <p>e) Behavioral Impact</p> <p>2. Other Delivery Methods:</p> <p>a) Conventional Delivery (Leaflets, Posters): The ability to share multiple messages simultaneously with the target audience. However, effectiveness is limited by challenges in ensuring users read and understand the materials.</p> <p>b) Instructor-Led Delivery (Presentations, Seminars): Success depends on the instructor’s ability to engage employees, measured by participation in interactive activities and group work. Effectiveness is limited by its static and potentially boring nature.</p> <p>c) Online Delivery (Emails, Interactive Applications): Effectiveness is hindered by the need for user self-motivation, with challenges in creating and evaluating comprehensive online programs.</p> <p>d) Simulation-Based Delivery (Simulated Phishing Emails): Effectiveness is measured by evaluating errors in employee responses to simulated phishing emails, followed by training to improve recognition and response.</p> <p>e) Educational Video Delivery: Effectiveness is assessed by the ability to hold trainees’ attention longer than conventional methods, using visual and audio learning to impart knowledge.</p>	No – Not described as adhering to specific standards.	Ying He et al. (2021)

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37	Video-Based	Not specified (Evaluated by Ghazvini & Shukur within TMS Framework)	Uses videos to deliver security training content, providing visual and auditory learning. Aimed at accessibility and ease of distribution. The TMS Map suggests moderate engagement but limited interactivity.	Video-based methods	Accidental (User): Errors from lack of knowledge, such as improper data sharing. Example: An employee disclosing sensitive data, unaware of policies shown in a video.	Confidentiality: Educates on data protection. Integrity: Promotes proper data handling.	Not specified in the document.	Yes: A standard training method in many organizations, though not uniquely standardized in the study	Arash Ghazvini et al. (2017)